

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

Hesketh Bank

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The **postal survey aimed** to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

77 participants from Hesketh Bank, Banks and Tarleton (13% response rate)

48% 50%

8% aged 18-44

71% aged 45-74

20% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast at Hesketh out Marsh = **3.02 km**

Mean distance to the River Douglas = **0.98 km**

experienced flooding and/or erosion

have noticed coastal change

concerned about climate change

have not heard about nature-based solutions

would accept managed realignment if people are not displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Planning restrictions

“Planning conditions are needed to prevent future inappropriate development in areas that should be turned over to natural processes as a method of defence”

2 A mix of options

“Mix of options based on data, research and trial projects”

3 Restoration/recreation of natural habitats

“Restoration/recreation of natural ecosystems such as salt marshes - we need to work with nature and this is an important area for wildlife”

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>

not confident they can influence local decisions

do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among Hesketh Bank respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

Airth

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

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63 participants from Airth, Skinflats and Grangemouth (9.5% response rate)

16% aged 18-44

60% aged 45-74

24% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast
(Inner Forth) = **1.48 km**

Mean distance to other rivers =
0.77 km

experienced
flooding and/or
erosion

have noticed
coastal change

concerned about
climate change

have not heard
about nature-
based solutions

would accept
managed realignment
if people are not
displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Planning restrictions

“Limit development as we are already on a flood plain”

2 A mix of options

“A mix of options is likely to be required to achieve effective local protection without adverse impacts on adjacent coastline”

3 Restoration/recreation of natural habitats

“Natural defenses tend to be more sustainable in the longer term and can have a climate positive impact”

not confident they can influence local decisions

do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among Airth respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

More info about the project:
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Resilient Coasts Survey Results

St Andrews

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The postal survey aimed to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

126 participants from St Andrews (21% response rate)

56% 42%

31% aged 18-44

50% aged 45-74

19% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast =
0.96 km

Mean distance to rivers=
0.78 km

19%
experienced
flooding and/or
erosion

62%
have noticed
coastal change

83%
concerned about
climate change

36%
have not heard
about nature-
based solutions

31%
would accept
managed realignment
if people are not
displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Dune restoration

“It's most natural and least intrusive”

2 A mix of options

“A mix of options to match the complex and composite issues that need to be addressed”

3 Restoration/recreation of natural habitats

“Restoration and recreation of natural ecosystems as it will protect the coastline from both erosion and flooding as well as encourage habitats and biodiversity, while also being a reasonable costing solution”

76%
not confident they can influence local decisions

29%
do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among St Andrews respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

Pensarn

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The **postal survey aimed** to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

62 participants from Pensarn, Abergele, Towyn and Kinmel Bay (10.3% response rate)

7% aged 18-44

58% aged 45-74

32% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast =
0.71 km

Mean distance to rivers =
0.65 km

experienced
flooding and/or
erosion

have noticed
coastal change

concerned about
climate change

have not heard
about nature-
based solutions

would accept
managed realignment
if people are not
displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Planning restrictions

“We need to protect our environment and make the most of existing resources rather than build on our precious land ”

2 A mix of options

“As time goes on, options can then be altered to coincide with any natural changes occurring”

3 Groynes

“The groynes are already there, they just need replacing with wood again or rocks. You need to see the area and judge accordingly [...] making the best you can to defend the area with the least amount of impact on the beauty of the area being taken away”

not confident they can influence local decisions

do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among Pensarn respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>

This is part of a study published as Apine, E. & Stojanovic, T. (2025). Community acceptance of nature-based solutions for coastal flood risk management. *People and Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.70182>

Project funders:

Natural
Environment
Research Council

Economic
and Social
Research Council